

Tokenization and Digital Twins: Negotiating Reality and Fiction

- Workshop Recap -

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Date: 18-19 March 2026

Location: ZIBR, Zug, Switzerland

On 18-19 March, the workshop on the Philosophy and Ethics of Tokenization and Digital Twins took place at ZIBR. Tokenization refers to the conversion of rights or assets into digital tokens. Digital twins are data-driven models of physical entities or processes. The workshop explored how reality and fiction are distinguished, determined, and negotiated in the interplay between both technological paradigms. It was hosted by my Chair for Philosophy & Blockchain.

I would like to express my gratitude to the participants for their thought-provoking contributions and the generous, appreciative atmosphere that makes joint intellectual engagement so rewarding. Scholars from various career stages, countries, and methodological traditions gathered to benefit from each other's work, whether work-in-progress or polished forthcoming material. As the presentations and discussions indicated, interdisciplinary cross-fertilization is essential to understand and shape these technologies and their effects.

Some points of convergence in the contributions include the following:

- It remains contested whether a given token or digital twin genuinely represents the intended part of reality or merely substitutes for it in a way that distorts or harms.
- Existing legal, ethical, and political frameworks are challenged especially by the impact of AI-driven, highly granular (attempted) representations of real people and things. Structurally novel problems are introduced that may require new conceptual vocabularies.
- Stakes are particularly high at the boundaries of intimate bodily and mental spheres, personhood and death.

Atay Kozlovski (Delft) kicked off the workshop with his keynote on the "Promise, Perils, and Ethics of a Growing Phenomenon." He argued that established typologies of digital twinning continue to elide important structural aspects and provided a novel proposal to capture these. This proposal reflects problem diagnoses from his recently published and forthcoming work [1, 2], in which he cautions that Digital Twins could act as Golems wandering off and Dybbuks taking over their hosts.

Ana Cláudia Barbosa (Porto) presented the foundations of her doctoral research on "Tokenizing the Dead: Feminist Posthumous Data Sovereignty and Spectral Digital Twins". Ana argued that AI-generated reconstructions of deceased persons convert the dead into commercially exploitable data assets, amounting to what she calls ontological kidnapping, a consequence that is particularly harmful to already marginalized groups.

Riccardo Valenti (PhD Venice & Paris) presented "Tokenized Absence: A Micro-Phenomenological Analysis of Deathbots as Digital Twins." The talk focused on the phenomenology of loss and meaning [3, 4]. Riccardo provided a fine-grained phenomenological analysis of virtual representations of deceased individuals, driven by insights on loss and grief from Husserl, Fink, Merleau-Ponty, Waldenfels and others. The analysis explored and evaluated affordances and shortfalls of a variety of deathbots, both hypothetical and already existing implementations.

Matthias Braun (Bonn) gave a keynote address entitled "Ending A Simulation Of Your Body: A Case of Fracticide?" It centered the question of how the artefactual nature of digital twins intersects with our existence as embodied selves. Likewise inspired by Merleau-Ponty [5], and weaving together themes from previously published as well as forthcoming works, including on the notion of "decommissioning" [6] a digital twin, he argued for the need to distinguish different dimensions of embodiment and of the integrity of bodies to understand the full impact of digital twinning. Having had the privilege of collaborating with Matthias in the past, it was a particularly special moment to welcome him at ZIBR.

ZIBR scholar Christoph Engel-Bunsas outlined his ongoing doctoral research on "Deepfakes". As a lawyer and professional opera singer, Christoph brought his unique first-personal outlook to bear on pressing normative issues related to how voice [7, 8] and other audiovisual data are susceptible to capture and exploitation. One strand of his research critically investigates the surprisingly common narrative that deepfake-related risks and challenges are already covered by existing legal frameworks, including on AI, IP, and data protection.

Emanuele Martinelli (Zurich), who is in the final stages of his PhD in Philosophy, presented a research agenda for tackling the philosophical dimensions of AI-driven activity in the economy. In light of Emanuele's doctoral work on the philosophy of agency [9] and the (in)ability of AI to model economic systems [10], he mapped out prospects for accelerating, amplifying, and governing AI agents through access to suitable infrastructures.

The second day of the workshop began with Muriel Leuenberger (Zurich). In her keynote address "When Should We Act for Ourselves?", Muriel proposed that the kind of delegation enacted by humans deploying digital twins can undermine necessary preconditions of a meaningful life (a connection which she has developed further in [11, 12], amongst others). The talk made a vivid case that proponents and users tend to refer to the notion of personalization in order to retain meaningfulness despite delegation, but that even setting aside issues of opacity, conservativeness, and calibration of digital twins, these attempts are ultimately in tension with how meaning in life is constituted.

Eike Düvel (Karlsruhe Institute of Technology) explored digital twins as tools in public deliberation. Digital twins could in principle compensate for various shortcomings in real-world democracies tackling short- and long-term decision problems [13, 14]. The notorious Habermas machine is only one (and a relatively crude) example of how digital applications could ameliorate deliberation and outcomes. Eike showed how assessments of the potentials and utility of digital twins will depend crucially on a set of specific questions broadly falling under the heading of accuracy, and on what we think democracy really is in the first place.

Georgy Ishmaev (INRIA) traced the "Moral Costs Of Incentives In Decentralized Systems". Drawing from his research on the Philosophy and Ethics of decentralized systems [e.g., 15, 16], Georgy showed how incentives that are indispensable for ensuring the stability of decentralized systems are in fact everywhere in social space. Crucially, the emergence of state-of-the-art architectures and agents could soon pose fundamentally new questions about who is in charge of setting the ends for which incentives structures impose costs and benefits. He made an unsettling but forceful case that existing normative frameworks seem unsuitable for even capturing risks related to these issues on the horizon, let alone for addressing them.

Jay Hani (MU Vienna) gave insights into his doctoral research on the significance of Blockchain infrastructures for the trading of energy data [17]. His talk was entitled "From Epistemology to Ontology: Blockchain Digital Twins and The Institutional Authority of Energy Data". It made a nuanced, practically grounded case that due to its ability to facilitate trustless verifiability, blockchain actually *de facto* turns records into ground truths. Amongst others, this introduces new questions about responsibility for errors and potentially false senses of certainty.

The workshop was concluded by ZIBR scholar Eli Guenzburger's talk on "Digital Twins and Artificial Life". This final presentation contributed two entirely new methodological approaches to the workshop: an investigation of the opportunities and limitations of representing living entities, first, through the lens of Early Modern Philosophy, and second, through the lens of (Theoretical) Biology. He demonstrated how both approaches contain resources to motivate skepticism about the possibility of producing genuine models of living entities by means of virtual artefacts. It is a great privilege for me to have the opportunity to supervise Eli's doctoral research at ZIBR.

This was the first workshop hosted by the Chair of Philosophy & Blockchain at ZIBR. The institute is a space for interdisciplinary exploration of societal issues raised by blockchain and decentralization. Future events are announced on zibr.ch.

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